

Original article

Divergent hypoglycemic and hyperglycemic responses to the components of evening meals. A general adult population study in individuals without diabetes (AEGIS study)

Tomás González-Vidal^{a, b, c, *}, Mar Calvo-Malvar^{d, e, g}, Carmen Fernández-Merino^{e, f, g}, Juan Sánchez-Castro^{e, f, g}, Óscar Lado-Baleato^{e, h}, Carla Díaz-Louzaoⁱ, Marcos Pazos-Couselo^{e, g, j}, Manuela Alonso-Sampedro^{e, g}, Marcos Matabuena^k, Francisco Gude^{e, j, l}

^a Department of Endocrinology and Nutrition, Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias/University of Oviedo, Spain

^b Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria del Principado de Asturias (ISPA), Oviedo, Spain

^c Department of Medicine, University of Oviedo, Spain

^d Department of Laboratory Medicine, University Clinical Hospital of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

^e Research Methods Group (RESMET), Health Research Institute of Santiago de Compostela (IDIS), Santiago de Compostela, Spain

^f A Estrada Primary Care Center, A Estrada, Spain

^g Network for Research on Chronicity, Primary Care, and Health Promotion (RICAPPS-ISCIII), Santiago de Compostela, Spain

^h ISCIII Support Platforms for Clinical Research, Health Research Institute of Santiago de Compostela, Spain

ⁱ Department of Mathematics, University of A Coruña, A Coruña, Spain

^j Department of Psychiatry, Radiology, Public Health, Nursing and Medicine, University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

^k Department of Biostatistics, Harvard University, Boston, MA 02115, USA

^l Concepción Arenal Primary Care Center, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 11 March 2024

Accepted 8 November 2024

Keywords:

Continuous glucose monitoring

Nutrient components

Postprandial glucose

Diet

SUMMARY

Background and aim: Few real-life studies have analyzed the glycemic response to nutrients in individuals without diabetes. We investigated the glycemic response to evening meals in relation to individual characteristics, nutrient components, and preprandial and postprandial routines.

Methods: A cross-sectional study of 489 individuals without diabetes from a randomly selected general adult population (310 women, median age 46 years, range 18–84 years) was conducted using a continuous glucose monitoring device for 7 days. The study recorded the participants' glycemic profile at 6 h after dinner, the food consumed at dinner, the fasting duration before dinner, and the duration between the end of dinner and going to bed. Principal component analysis and multilevel functional data analysis were used to interpret the data.

Results: On average, a postprandial glycemic peak was observed at 45 min, followed by a decline to baseline levels from 90 min onwards. Older age, higher body mass index, and large meals (especially those high in starch and dairy products) were all significantly associated with higher glucose levels throughout the 6 h after dinner. The fruit component was associated with a higher initial glycemic peak, followed by a lowering glycemic effect thereafter ($p < 0.001$). The alcohol component was associated with an initial hypoglycemic effect ($p = 0.006$). The participants who fasted longer before dinner had higher postprandial glycemic peaks ($p = 0.001$), and those who went to bed later had higher postprandial glucose levels than those who went to bed earlier ($p = 0.003$).

Conclusions: The participants' characteristics, nutrient components, and pre- and post-dinner routines have divergent effects on post-dinner glycemic response.

© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CGM, continuous glucose monitoring; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; MARD, mean absolute relative difference; PCA, principal component analysis; T2D, type 2 diabetes.

* Corresponding author. Department of Endocrinology and Nutrition, Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias, Avenida de Roma s/n, 33011, Oviedo, Spain.

E-mail address: uo302763@uniovi.es (T. González-Vidal).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2024.11.020>

0261-5614/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Diet plays a key role in preventing metabolic diseases such as type 2 diabetes (T2D). A caloric surplus maintained over time (produced by excessive eating accompanied by low physical activity) will inevitably lead to obesity and excess adiposity [1], which will consequently increase peripheral insulin resistance [2], predisposing the individual to hyperglycemia and the development of T2D [3,4]. Especially in those with obesity, the risk of developing T2D will be greater if they frequently consume foods that significantly raise postprandial blood glucose levels [5], such as soft drinks and sugary juices [6,7]. In contrast, the consumption of foods without added sugar, such as fruits, vegetables, fish, and whole grains, has been shown to reduce the risk of T2D [8]. Individuals with T2D have a higher incidence of cardiovascular disease [9]. Moreover, even in people without T2D, elevated postprandial glycemia is independently associated with cardiovascular disease [10] and mortality [11]. Therefore, it is of interest to determine the blood glucose response to the intake of various nutrients in order to implement dietary strategies for the prevention of cardiovascular disease.

It is well known that a large intake of carbohydrates is related to greater postprandial hyperglycemia, especially in the case of carbohydrates with a high glycemic index or rapid absorption [12]. In contrast, there are nutritional strategies that help attenuate postprandial hyperglycemia, such as starting meals with a serving of vegetables [13] or protein [14]. In individuals without diabetes and with appropriate insulin sensitivity, this postprandial hyperglycemic peak tends to return to normal as time passes. In certain patients, especially those with rapid gastric emptying, the elevated insulin secretion generated by ingesting sugary foods can even lead to hypoglycemia 2–5 h after ingestion [15]. Alcohol, a common component of many adults' diet, can cause hypoglycemia, which in this case is not mediated by insulin but by the inhibition of hepatic gluconeogenesis [16,17].

By employing continuous glucose monitoring (CGM), several studies have analyzed the response of interstitial glucose to the intake of various nutrients. Given that the typical users of CGM systems are patients with diabetes, most of these studies have been conducted on patients with diabetes [18–21]. There are, however, similar studies with healthy populations [22–32]. In general, studies conducted with healthy populations agree that postprandial hyperglycemia is directly proportional to the amount of carbohydrates ingested [24,25,29], especially if they are high glycemic index carbohydrates [26,31,32], and that fiber [22,24,29], fat [22,25,29], and protein intake [22,25] could attenuate the postprandial hyperglycemic peak. These studies employed a similar methodology in almost all cases: starting with a standardized diet, the differences in postprandial hyperglycemia were compared, depending on the participants' characteristics [23,25] or the ingested nutrients [22,25–32]. To date, very few studies have been conducted in real-life conditions, i.e., giving participants the freedom to eat whatever they wanted at all times. In a previous work from the A-Estrada Glycation and Inflammation Study (AEGIS), we have observed that the effects of macronutrients (carbohydrates, fats, and proteins) and fiber on CGM metrics differed between men and women [24]. Furthermore, we have developed statistical methods to investigate nonlinear relationships between diet and glucose data from CGM by means of functional data analyses, using the effects of macronutrients and fiber in a subset of the AEGIS study as an example [33]. An additional problem for statistical analysis in this scenario is that, beyond macronutrients, a free diet can have a high heterogeneity of nutrients, thereby making their accurate quantification and analysis difficult. For that purpose, statistical tools such as principal

component analysis (PCA) can help identify the various main elements (in this case, nutrients) that make up a set; i.e., PCA intends dimensionality reduction to simplify a large data set into a smaller set while still maintaining significant patterns and trends. Additionally, components from PCA are mutually independent, which simplifies their inclusion in any multivariate regression model, such as multilevel functional data analysis. The present study aimed to investigate the hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic effects of nutrient components from evening meals in an adult general population using CGM by means of PCA and multilevel functional data analysis [33].

2. Methods

2.1. Study design and setting

This cross-sectional study included a subset of individuals enrolled in the A-Estrada Glycation and Inflammation Study (AEGIS, NCT01796184; www.clinicaltrials.gov). A detailed description of the study has been published elsewhere [34]. The study was conducted in the municipality of A-Estrada, Spain. An age-stratified random sample of the population aged 18 years and older was drawn from Spain's National Health System Registry, which covers more than 95 % of the Spanish population. A subsample of 622 individuals was recruited from the total of 1516 AEGIS participants for a 7-day CGM procedure (Fig. 1). Subsets of this sample were included in previous studies of the effect of macronutrients on CGM metrics in relation to sex [24] and to design statistical tools for multilevel functional data analysis [33]. From March 2013 to March 2015, participants were successively convened at the A-Estrada Primary Care Center (A-Estrada, Spain), where they 1) completed a structured questionnaire that collected demographic and anthropometric data; 2) provided information on their lifestyle, including diet, physical activity, alcohol consumption and smoking; 3) provided a fasting venous blood sample; and 4) were prepared for CGM (see below). A total of 41 individuals were excluded due to non-compliance with the CGM protocol ($n = 4$) or difficulties in handling the device ($n = 37$); 80 were not included because they met the American Diabetes Association criteria for diabetes mellitus [35]. The present study focused on evening meals to minimize additional elements such as supplementary intake, physical activity, and stress that could influence CGM after breakfast or lunch. We excluded individuals who had taken any additional food item just before bedtime ($n = 12$) to ensure the accuracy of the data related to the effects of the evening meal's composition on glucose response. The final study population therefore included 489 participants (310 women [63.4 %]; median age 46 years, range 18–84 years) (Fig. 1).

2.2. Main determinations

2.2.1. Lifestyle variables

2.2.1.1. Assessment of physical activity. All participants underwent the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (short form). The metabolic equivalents of task were calculated [36] and participants were classified as either inactive, minimally active, or health-enhancing physical activity active.

2.2.1.2. Alcohol consumption and smoking. Alcohol consumption was recorded in terms of standard drinking units by adding up the number of glasses of wine (approx. 10 g of alcohol per glass), bottles of beer (approx. 10 g per 200 mL), and units of spirits (approx. 20 g per measure) regularly consumed per week [37]. Smoking was recorded as the number of cigarettes regularly consumed per day. Consumers of at least one cigarette per day were considered

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the study.

smokers. Individuals who had quit smoking during the preceding year were considered smokers.

2.2.2. Laboratory determinations

Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), serum glucose, and serum insulin levels were determined in fresh fasting samples. Insulin resistance was estimated using the homeostasis model assessment method [38].

2.2.3. Nutrient composition and habits

During the CGM assessment period (see below), the participants monitored their food and drink intake. The participants were instructed not to make changes in their usual diet and physical exercise. For 7 consecutive days (including 6 dinners, and at least one weekend or holiday), the participants were asked to record their diet at the time that food and beverages were consumed. They were also asked about the time of the meal consumption, food

items included in the menu or in the recipes, the preparation method, condiments added, product brands, and the amount consumed. Whenever possible, the food was weighed; household measures, such as cups and spoons, could be used if exact measurements of weight were not possible. Dinner times, previous fasting period, and the time elapsed between the end of dinner and going to bed were also recorded. At the end of the assessment period, a research dietician reviewed the intake records and asked for additional data when records appeared incomplete or implausible.

Specific software (DIAL®; DIALEXE Version 3.15, December 2021, Alce Ingeniería, Spain) was employed to calculate the energy and nutrients provided by the food [39,40]. This tool uses the Food Composition Tables published by the Department of Nutrition of the Complutense University of Madrid in 2010. The food items not included in the program were created based on the information provided by participants (e.g., food packages) or databases such as

the Spanish Food Composition Database (Red BEDCA) [41] or FoodData Central of the US Department of Agriculture [42].

2.2.4. Continuous glucose monitoring data collection

At the start of monitoring period, a research nurse inserted an Enlite™ sensor (Medtronic Inc, USA) subcutaneously in the participant's abdomen and instructed the participant in the care of the connected iPro™ model CGM device (Medtronic Inc, USA). The iPro™ is a blind CGM system that provides retrospective information on glucose profiles. Given that the system does not provide data on glucose levels during its use, the subjects' routines were not affected. The sensor continuously measures the interstitial glucose concentrations, recording and storing values (range 40–400 mg/dL) every 5 min. On day 7, the sensor was removed before dinner time and the data were downloaded, disregarding the results from the first day. If the data acquisition failed more than 2 h in a day, the entire day's data were discarded.

The participants were also provided with a OneTouch™ Verio™ Pro glucometer (LifeScan, USA), lancets and test strips. To ensure the reliability of the CGM data, the participants were instructed to perform at least 3 capillary blood glucose measurements per day (usually before the main meals) to calibrate the iPro™. CGM data that could not be calibrated with ≥ 3 capillary glucose controls per day were excluded. The overall sensor accuracy expressed as the mean absolute relative difference (MARD) was 7.9%. The MARD was 7.8% when glucose levels were 70–180 mg/dL, 9.5% when >180 mg/dL, and 29.2% when <70 mg/dL. The MARDs for all capillary-sensor glucose paired points stratified by day (1–6) were 12.1%, 7.6%, 7.0%, 7.1%, 7.3%, and 6.6%, respectively. Data from day 1 were therefore excluded from analysis, as previously mentioned.

Mean glucose, standard deviation [43,44], coefficient of variation [43,45], mean of daily differences [46], mean amplitude of glycemic excursions [44,45], area under the curve [45], time below range (percentage of the day during which the subject has interstitial glucose levels <70 mg/dL), time in range (70–180 mg/dL), and time above range (>180 mg/dL) were measured.

2.3. Ethical issues

The study was approved by the Regional Ethics Committee (code 2012-025) and conformed to the current Helsinki Declaration. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

2.4. Statistical analyses

Continuous variables were summarized as medians and interquartile ranges, while categorical variables were presented as absolute and relative frequencies. Differences between participants with and without any post-dinner glucose peak ≥ 140 mg/dL regarding evening meal composition were tested using linear mixed models. Differences in other continuous variables were tested using the Mann–Whitney test. The Spearman rank test was used to assess correlation.

To investigate the contribution of the nutrient composition of the evening meals, as well as preprandial and postprandial habits, adjusting for the effects of age, sex, and body mass index (BMI) on the post-dinner glucose response, a two-phase analysis was conducted. First, the nutrient composition of the evening meals was analyzed using PCA to reduce dimensionality and obtain a set of independent variables for use as predictor variables. The optimal number of dimensions explaining the variability of the original data was based on the elbow criteria. Then, these dimensions, along with the clinical variables, were related to postprandial glucose response in a multilevel functional regression model based on Matabuena et al. [33,47]. This computational approach is efficient

and allows us to accommodate different random effect structures, such as individual variability and the interaction between individuals and the number of meals with random slopes, in a functional multilevel regression model.

From a practical standpoint for scientific application analysis, the underlying mathematical model is expressed as follows (for a specific time point t , ranging from 0 to 360 in 5-min intervals, for the j^{th} dinner of the i^{th} participant):

$$\begin{aligned} CGM_{ij}(t) = & \beta_0(t) + PC1_{ij}\beta_1(t) + PC2_{ij}\beta_2(t) + PC3_{ij}\beta_3(t) \\ & + PC4_{ij}\beta_4(t) + PC5_{ij}\beta_5(t) + Fastingtime_{ij}\beta_6(t) \\ & + Timesleep_{ij}\beta_7(t) + Age_i\beta_8(t) + Sex_i\beta_9(t) \\ & + BMI_i\beta_{10}(t) + u_{i0}(t) + \varepsilon_{ij}(t) \end{aligned}$$

... where $u_{i0} \in N(0, \sigma(t))$ is the individual error term, which is independent of the model error $\varepsilon_{ij}(t)$. This standard linear mixed model is fitted 72 times, once for each location of t . After this pointwise fit, a cubic spline basis was used to smooth each $\beta_k(t)$ (for $k = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8$) coefficient separately.

In the context of our mathematical model, $\varepsilon_{ij}(t)$ represents the random error associated with the i^{th} participant and j^{th} dinner at a specific time point t . The term $u_{i0}(t)$ signifies individual random effects, modelled as a Gaussian process with a mean of zero, denoted as $GP(0, \Sigma_i)$. This approach accounts for the inherent variability unique to each participant over time.

The time-dependent statistical association of the glucose response with the fixed effects specified by diet, sex, and age is defined in terms of the coefficients $\beta(t)$. These coefficients, expressed in terms of cubic splines, capture the intricate dynamics of the relationship between the predictors and the glucose response over the specified time intervals. This flexible representation allows us to uncover nuanced patterns and trends within the data, which is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the underlying physiological processes.

Additionally, given the complexity of functional data analyses, linear mixed model analyses were conducted using the same predictor variables as in the previous model, where the response variable was the average glucose level in the postprandial period (0–2 h, 2–6 h, and the entire period).

In the realm of data visualization and interpretation, all analyses were meticulously conducted using R software, incorporating essential libraries such as *ggplot2* for plotting, *flextable* for results reporting, *factoextra* for PCA, and *refund*, *fda* and *lme4* for functional regression model fitting.

3. Results

The main characteristics of the study population are shown in Table 1A. The number of evening meals per participant varied because a number of the participants did not have dinner daily. Most of the participants (55.6%) had 5 available evening meals, 17.9% had 4, 14.3% had 3, 8.6% had 2, and 3.5% had a single available evening meal. In our sample, dinner typically occurred at 21:59, with 90% of the meals occurring between 19:50 and 23:30 (Fig. 2). The total number of evening meals included for analysis was 2023. The median calorie intake of the evening meals was 562 calories, with 25% of the meals falling below 377 calories and 25% exceeding 827 calories (Table 1B). Notably, the evening meals included a higher median carbohydrate content than protein and lipid content. Alcohol consumption exceeded 10 g in 15.9% of the evening meals (Table 1B).

Table 1A shows a comparison of the participants' features (including CGM metrics) who had at least one dinner with a high postprandial glucose peak (≥ 140 mg/dL) and those who did not. High postprandial glucose peaks were associated with older age,

Table 1
(A) Characteristics of participants and (B) composition of dinners in relation to the highest postprandial glucose peak.

(A) Characteristics of participants				
	Total sample (489 individuals)	Postprandial glucose peak		P-value
		<140 mg/dL (191 individuals)	≥140 mg/dL ^a (298 individuals)	
Age (years)	46.0 (36.0, 58.0)	43.0 (32.0, 52.5)	49.0 (38.0, 60.0)	<0.001
Sex (woman), n (%)	310 (63.4)	115 (60.2)	195 (65.4)	0.283
Smoking status, n (%)				0.410
Non smoker	264 (54.0)	96 (50.3)	168 (56.4)	
Ex smoker	124 (25.4)	53 (27.7)	71 (23.8)	
Current smoker	101 (20.7)	42 (22.0)	59 (19.8)	
Alcohol consumption (g/day)	20.0 (3.0, 80.0)	30.0 (4.0, 100.0)	10.0 (3.0, 70.0)	0.020
Physical activity				0.235
Low	175 (35.8)	62 (32.5)	113 (37.9)	
Medium	185 (37.8)	71 (37.2)	114 (38.3)	
High	129 (49.9)	58 (30.4)	71 (23.8)	
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	27.3 (23.9, 30.8)	26.9 (23.9, 30.2)	27.4 (24.2, 31.1)	0.269
Hb1Ac (%)	5.3 (5.2, 5.5)	5.3 (5.1, 5.4)	5.4 (5.2, 5.6)	<0.001
Fasting serum glucose (mg/dL)	87.0 (80.0, 94.0)	84.0 (79.0, 92.0)	88.0 (81.0, 95.0)	<0.001
HOMA-IR (μ units/mL * mg/dL)	2.2 (1.6, 3.1)	2.1 (1.6, 3.0)	2.3 (1.6, 3.3)	0.144
Continuous glucose monitoring				
Mean glucose (mg/dL)	104.6 (99.0, 110.2)	100.2 (95.9, 104.7)	107.8 (101.9, 113.5)	<0.001
Standard deviation (mg/dL)	14.7 (12.1, 17.8)	12.1 (10.2, 14.6)	16.5 (13.9, 19.4)	<0.001
Coefficient of variation (%)	13.9 (11.7, 16.9)	12.4 (10.3, 14.6)	15.3 (12.8, 18.4)	<0.001
MODD (mmol/L)	0.7 (0.5, 0.8)	0.6 (0.5, 0.7)	0.7 (0.6, 0.9)	<0.001
MAGE (mg/dL)	26.5 (21.8, 32.2)	22.3 (18.4, 26.6)	29.8 (24.8, 35.8)	<0.001
AUC (mg/min/dl)	104.5 (98.9, 110.1)	100.1 (95.9, 104.6)	107.7 (101.9, 113.5)	<0.001
Time below range (%)	0.00 (0.00, 1.69)	0.00 (0.00, 1.93)	0.00 (0.00, 1.61)	0.575
Time in range (%)	99.74 (97.72, 100.00)	100.00 (98.07, 100.00)	99.61 (97.65, 100.00)	0.058
Time above range (%)	0.00 (0.00, 0.00)	0.00 (0.00, 0.00)	0.00 (0.00, 0.19)	<0.001

(B) Composition of dinners				
	Total sample (2023 dinners)	Postprandial glucose peak		P-value
		<140 mg/dL (1389 dinners)	≥140 mg/dL ^b (634 dinners)	
Calories (kcal)	562 (377, 827)	550 (372, 807)	590 (384, 865)	0.002
Proteins (g)	23.8 (14.9, 36.6)	23.5 (14.8, 35.8)	24.3 (15.0, 37.5)	0.051
Carbohydrates (g)	51.2 (31.0, 78.4)	48.7 (29.3, 74.9)	57.0 (34.6, 83.5)	<0.001
Starch (g)	27.5 (13.2, 47.0)	26.0 (12.0, 45.1)	31.6 (16.9, 50.8)	<0.001
Simple sugars (g)	17.3 (7.2, 30.4)	16.7 (6.7, 28.9)	18.6 (8.5, 32.5)	0.003
Soluble fibre (g)	1.1 (0.4, 1.9)	1.1 (0.4, 1.9)	1.3 (0.5, 2.1)	0.044
Insoluble fibre (g)	1.8 (0.8, 3.0)	1.8 (0.8, 2.9)	1.8 (0.8, 3.1)	0.199
Vegetal fibre (g)	4.3 (2.5, 7.2)	4.3 (2.5, 7.1)	4.3 (2.6, 7.2)	0.104
Lipids (g)	23.8 (12.3, 37.9)	23.7 (12.6, 37.7)	24.1 (11.2, 38.9)	0.318
Alcohol (>10 g), n (%)	322 (15.9)	241 (17.4)	81 (12.8)	0.030

Data are medians and interquartile ranges (within parentheses) or absolute numbers and percentages (within parentheses). HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin. HOMA-IR, homeostasis model assessment method for insulin resistance (fasting concentration of serum insulin [μ units/mL] x serum glucose [mg/dL]/405). MAGE, mean amplitude of glycemic excursions. MODD, mean of daily differences. AUC, area under the curve. Time in range, glucose 70–180 mg/dL; Time below range, glucose <70 mg/dL; Time above range, glucose >180 mg/dL.

^a Patients with at least one dinner in which postprandial glucose exceeded 140 mg/dL were categorized in this group; the remaining ones had postprandial values below this threshold for all dinners.

^b All dinners in which postprandial glucose exceeded 140 mg/dL were categorized in this group.

Fig. 2. Timing of evening meals. Pre- and post-dinner routines.

lower alcohol consumption, higher concentrations of fasting serum glucose, and higher HbA1c levels. Additionally, subjects who reached the 140 mg/dL threshold during at least one dinner exhibited greater glycemic variability (greater standard deviation, coefficient of variation, mean amplitude of glycemic excursions, mean of daily differences, and area under the curve) and more hyperglycemic features (higher mean glucose and longer time above range) (Table 1A).

Table 1B shows the composition of dinners that had postprandial glucose peaks ≥ 140 mg/dL and those dinners in which glucose did not reach that threshold. High postprandial glucose peaks were also associated with higher calorie, soluble fiber, and carbohydrate content in the evening meal (particularly, starch and simple sugars). In contrast, dinners with high postprandial glucose peaks had lower alcohol content (Table 1).

Figure 3 shows an example of the postprandial glucose curves for 2 participants after 5 and 4 evening meals, respectively. This figure shows that the peak glucose value and rate of decrease exhibited significant variations among the participants and within a given individual.

The variability in evening meal composition was effectively captured by the first 5 dimensions of the PCA, collectively explaining 75.3 % of the original data variability. Importantly, each of the 5 dimensions identified by PCA corresponded to distinct features of the evening meals that hold specific nutritional interpretations (Table 2), as follows:

- The main contributors to dimension 1 were calories, lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates, and was therefore labelled as *food quantity*.

Fig. 3. Example of the postprandial glucose curves for 2 participants after 5 and 4 evening meals, respectively.

Table 2 Spearman correlation coefficients between nutrients and components from PCA (principal component analysis).

	Component 1 <i>quantity</i>	Component 2 <i>fruit</i>	Component 3 <i>dairy</i>	Component 4 <i>starch</i>	Component 5 <i>alcohol</i>
Alcohol (g)	0.30	-0.11	-0.15	0.07	0.64
Calories (kcal)	0.93	-0.16	0.06	0.05	-0.05
Carbohydrates (g)	0.70	0.22	0.26	0.42	-0.09
Cholesterol (g)	0.64	-0.39	-0.02	-0.23	-0.14
Fructose (g)	0.38	0.73	-0.22	-0.40	0.00
Galactose (g)	0.16	0.14	0.09	-0.07	-0.15
Glucose (g)	0.41	0.72	-0.19	-0.40	0.04
Insoluble fiber (g)	0.57	0.54	-0.42	0.02	-0.20
Lactose (g)	0.07	0.05	0.72	0.13	-0.09
Lipids (g)	0.81	-0.37	-0.02	-0.26	-0.16
Maltose (g)	0.19	0.02	0.17	0.07	0.33
Monounsaturated fats (g)	0.78	-0.33	-0.13	-0.27	-0.13
Polyunsaturated fats (g)	0.75	-0.31	-0.14	-0.19	-0.14
Proteins (g)	0.77	-0.25	-0.00	0.00	-0.11
Saturated fats (g)	0.70	-0.39	0.23	-0.20	-0.17
Simple sugars (g)	0.39	0.52	0.64	-0.13	0.12
Soluble fiber (g)	0.62	0.43	-0.41	0.16	-0.22
Starch (g)	0.64	-0.03	-0.03	0.59	-0.18
Sucrose (g)	0.38	0.53	0.36	-0.24	-0.04
Vegetable fiber (g)	0.67	0.44	-0.18	0.22	-0.13
Water (g)	0.62	0.31	0.06	-0.10	0.41

Correlations greater than 0.50 between nutrients and components from PCA are shown in bold.

- The main contributors to dimension 2 were fructose, glucose, insoluble fiber, and sucrose, and was therefore labelled as *fruit*.
- The main contributors to dimension 3 were lactose, simple sugars, sucrose, and saturated fats, and was therefore labelled as *dairy*.
- The main contributors to dimension 4 were starch and complex carbohydrates, and was therefore labelled as *starch*.
- The main contributors to dimension 5 were alcohol, maltose, and water, and was therefore labelled as *alcohol*.

Table 3 represents the 5 evening meals with the highest and lowest values in each of the 5 dimensions and illustrates their main contributors (high-calorie meal for dimension 1, fruits for dimension 2, milk derivatives and dairy products for dimension 3, grain products for dimension 4, and alcoholic beverages for dimension 5).

Table 3
Characteristics of the five dinners corresponding to the highest and lowest values for each dimension, obtained from principal component analysis of nutrients.

	Dinners with the lowest values	Dinners with the highest values
Dimension 1 Labelled as <i>food quantity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID 1335 (08/02/2015): chamomile tea (280 mL). - ID 0777 (20/02/2014): fat-free, sugar free yogurt (125 g). - ID 1258 (18/12/2014): fat-free, sugar free yogurt (125 g) + water (200 mL). - ID 1258 (20/12/2014): fat-free, sugar free yogurt (125 g) + water (200 mL). - ID 0475 (18/08/2013): 1 coffee (100 mL) + 2 tea spoons of white sugar. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID 0743 (29/01/2014): pizza (800 g). - ID 1255 (13/12/2014): Spanish ham (50 g) + cured cheese (6 slices) + pork "secreto" (200 g) + fries + wine (1 cup) + 1 coffee with 10 g of sugar + 2 liquor shots (restaurant dinner). - ID 1244 (06/12/2014): 2 beers + fried squids + pork meat with potatoes + coffee cake + 2 liquor shots + rum with coke (restaurant dinner). - ID 0187 (19/04/2013): stewed wild boar with potatoes + stewed rabbit with potatoes + almond cake + ice cream cake + red wine with sweet soda + coke (330 mL) + 2 coffees (restaurant dinner). - ID 0146 (23/03/2013): ½ banana +2 kiwis +1 apple + 1 pear + sweetened yogurt + bread (50 g) + sardines in oil (70 g) + quince paste (60 g) + cheese (110 g) + black chocolate with almonds (60 g) + 8 cookies + glass of water. - ID 0973 (29/05/2014): strawberries (650 g). - ID 0777 (19/02/2014): 1 apple + 1 kiwi + 1 orange + 1 fat-free, sugar-free yogurt. - ID 0381 (05/07/2013): 1 apple + 1 pear + 1 apricot + 1 peach. - ID 0002 (19/09/2012): 2 slices of pineapple + 2 peaches + 1 yogurt. - ID 0981 (06/06/2014): 1 banana + 1 apple + cherries (100 g) + water (1 glass).
Dimension 2 Labelled as <i>fruit</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID 0511 (04/09/2013): grilled pork steak (200 g) + 2 glasses of wine. - ID 0007 (26/11/2012): French omelette (2 eggs) + 3 slices of cheese + 2 glasses of water. - ID 1209 (08/11/2014): 2 sausages + 2 boiled offs + chorizo (30 g) + bechamel sauce (270 g) + zero coke (330 mL) - ID 0091 (13/02/2013): 2 burgers + 4 slices of cheese + 2 slices of York ham + fries + light coke (330 mL). - ID 1213 (12/11/2014): French omelette (2 eggs) + water (500 mL). - ID 0025 (17/12/2012): cod with potatoes and string beans + bread (75 g) + wine (1.5 glasses). - ID 0578 (18/10/2013): nuts (106 g) + pear (116 g) + apple (123 g) + bread (74 g) + wine (1.5 glasses). - ID 1435 (08/03/2015): Galician stew (500 g) + wine (2 glasses) + bread (70 g) - ID 0137 (18/03/2013): chard scramble (2 eggs). - ID 1108 (09/09/2014): string beans (125 g) + carrots (95 g) + tomato salad (264 g) + beetroot (135 g) + bread (47 g) + water (400 mL). - ID 0983 (05/06/2014): double burger + coke (500 mL). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID 1217 (13/01/2015): stracciatella yogurt (350 g). - D 1217 (14/01/2015): stracciatella yogurt (350 g). - ID 1195 (01/11/2014): lemon yogurt (250 g) + wild fruit yogurt (250 g) + water (200 mL). - ID 1192 (29/10/2014): smashed potatoes (217 g) + tuna (46 g) + bread (5 g) + 21 pistachios + water (200 mL) + vanilla yogurt (500 g). - ID 0474 (15/11/2013): fried wheat snacks (25 g) + chocolate cookies (48 g) + yogurt (250 g) + water (200 mL). - ID 0275 (24/05/2013): whole grain breakfast cereals (1 bowl) + 1 soja yogurt (125 g). - ID 0119 (06/03/2013): poached hake (140 g) + boiled pees (70 g) + whole wheat bread (30 g). - ID 0740 (30/01/2014): gelatin + milk (1 cup) + oat (80 g) + 1 tea. - ID 1435 (08/03/2015): Galician stew with potatoes (500 g) + wine (40 cl) + bread (70 g). - ID 0434 (23/07/2013): boiled potatoes (100 g) + pees (300 g) + bread (60 g) + water (1 L). - ID 0636 (09/11/2013): 3 beers + 1 gin-tonic. - ID 1214 (15/11/2014): boiled potatoes (50 g) + pig ear (300 g) + bread (50 g) + roasted chestnuts (100 g) + king's cake (200 g) + wine (500 mL) + whiskey with coke (50 mL and 200 mL). - ID 1354 (13/02/2015): grilled beef (100 g) + custard with cream + octopus (100 g) + beer (1 L). - ID 1123 (16/09/2014): bread (152 g) + chorizo (57 g) + York ham (7 g) + radler beer (330 mL). - ID 0367 (23/06/213): beef sandwich + chorizo sandwich + beer (1 L).
Dimension 3 Labelled as <i>dairy</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID 1484 (19/03/2015): grilled beef (300 g) + 2 cokes (660 mL) + cheese custard (102 g). - ID 0494 (27/08/2013): watermelon (860 g) + 2 eggs + cheese (230 g) + quince paste (150 g). - ID 1137 (25/09/2014): scrambled eggs (100 g) + tomato sauce (50 g) + water (250 mL) + 1 yogurt drink with plant stanols (65 mL). - ID 0007 (26/11/2012): French omelette (2 eggs) + 3 slices of cheese + water (2 glasses). 	
Dimension 4 Labelled as <i>starch</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID 1041 (06/07/2014): chips + pistachios + sunflower seeds + peanuts. - ID 0638 (05/11/2013): sandwich with Turkey ham (33g) + cheese (28g) + 1 peach + 1 banana +1 coconut yogurt + water. - ID 1146 (05/10/2014): lettuce (300 g) + mussels (70 g) + bread (150 g) + 2 yogurts (250 g) + 1 plum. - ID 0081 (05/02/2013): sandwich with Spanish ham + 2 yogurts (250 g) + water (2 glasses). - ID 1259 (20/12/2014): bread (48 g) + cheese (24 g) + quince paste (43 g) + vanilla yogurt (125 g) + 1 banana + zero coke (200 mL). 	
Dimension 5 Labelled as <i>alcohol</i>		

ID (identification [participant number]). The date of the dinner is indicated within parentheses. The most representative dinner elements for each dimension are highlighted in bold.

Figure 4 displays the results of the multilevel functional regression model with postprandial glucose curves as the response. The predictor variables were the 5 PCA dimensions collecting the nutrient composition, demographic factors (age and sex), BMI, and factors related to routines before and after dinner, including the fasting period before dinner and the time until bedtime after dinner (in hours). The model intercept represents the mean shape of the postprandial glucose trajectory after removing the influence of evening meal composition and remaining factors. Following food intake (time = 0), the curve shows an increase until 45 min after the meal, reaching its peak value. Approximately 90 min after food intake, the glucose concentrations returned to baseline levels. Table 4A shows the median values of the CGM metrics over the 6-h post-dinner period, separating the early period (0–2 h) and the late period (2–6 h). Mean glucose in the postprandial period was

Fig. 4. Multilevel functional regression model with postprandial glucose curves as response. The predictor variables were the five PCA dimensions collecting dinner nutrients composition; clinical-demographic factors including age, sex and body mass index; and factors related to routines before and after dinner, including the fasting period before dinner, and the time until bedtime after dinner. The intercept (upper left panel) represents the mean shape of the postprandial glucose curve after removing the influence of dinner composition and the remaining factors. The independent effect of dinner nutrient components and additional factors are represented in the remaining curves, with their 95 % confidence intervals. The Y axis represents the independent regression coefficient (beta) for each factor. The beta coefficient is dynamic throughout the post-dinner period, which is represented on the X axis. The value of zero on the Y axis means that there is no effect of the corresponding factor with respect to the reference curve (intercept). Specific situations are commented in the text. Periods in which the 95 % confidence interval does not include the null effect are statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4

(A) Continuous glucose monitoring metrics in the 6 h after dinner. (B) Effect of dinner components, dinner timing, and participant characteristics on mean postprandial glucose levels in the 6 h after eating.

(A) Continuous glucose monitoring metrics after dinner in study participants (n = 489)						
Continuous glucose monitoring metrics	Entire postprandial period (0–6 h) Median (IQR)		Early postprandial period (0–2 h) Median (IQR)		Late postprandial period (2–6 h) Median (IQR)	
Mean glucose (mg/dL)	108.8 (100.3, 188.7)		114.0 (104.4, 124.6)		105.8 (96.7, 116.7)	
Standard deviation (mg/dL)	10.0 (6.7, 14.6)		8.4 (5.3, 12.7)		6.8 (4.4, 10.6)	
AUC (mg/min/dl)	108.9 (100.4, 118.7)		114.2 (104.6, 124.9)		103.6 (94.7, 114.3)	
Time below range (%)	0.00 (0.00, 0.00)		0.00 (0.00, 0.00)		0.00 (0.00, 0.00)	
Time in range (%)	100.00 (100.00, 100.00)		100.00 (100.00, 100.00)		100.00 (100.00, 100.00)	
Time above range (%)	0.00 (0.00, 0.00)		0.00 (0.00, 0.00)		0.00 (0.00, 0.00)	

(B) Effect of dinner components, dinner timing, and participant characteristics on mean postprandial glucose levels. Linear mixed model analyses (n = 2023)						
Dinner components, dinner timing, and participant characteristics	Entire postprandial period (0–6 h)		Early postprandial period (0–2 h)		Late postprandial period (2–6 h)	
	Coefficient (SE)	P value	Coefficient (SE)	P value	Coefficient (SE)	P value
Intercept	90.0 (3.1)	<0.001	97.4 (3.5)	<0.001	86.0 (3.3)	<0.001
Dinner components						
Component 1 (Food quantity)	0.7 (0.1)	<0.001	0.3 (0.1)	0.017	0.9 (0.1)	<0.001
Component 2 (Fruits)	−0.4 (0.2)	0.009	0.1 (0.2)	0.968	−0.6 (0.2)	<0.001
Component 3 (Dairy)	0.9 (0.2)	<0.001	0.9 (0.3)	<0.001	0.9 (0.2)	<0.001
Component 4 (Starch)	1.1 (0.2)	<0.001	1.6 (0.3)	<0.001	0.8 (0.3)	0.002
Component 5 (Alcohol)	−0.3 (0.3)	0.214	−0.9 (0.3)	0.006	−0.1 (0.3)	0.736
Dinner timing						
Fasting period (minutes)	0.2 (0.1)	0.181	0.5 (0.2)	0.001	0.1 (0.1)	0.994
Time until sleep (minutes)	0.6 (0.2)	0.003	0.1 (0.2)	0.839	0.9 (0.2)	<0.001
Individuals' characteristics						
Age (years)	0.2 (0.1)	<0.001	0.2 (0.1)	<0.001	0.2 (0.1)	<0.001
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	0.3 (0.1)	0.010	0.2 (0.1)	0.070	0.4 (0.1)	<0.001
Sex (man)	−0.9 (1.1)	0.351	−2.7 (1.2)	0.026	−0.1 (1.1)	0.949

Results are presented for the entire postprandial period (6 h) and divided into an early phase (0–2 h) and a late phase (2–6 h). Continuous glucose monitoring metrics (Table A) are presented as medians and interquartile ranges (within parentheses). All listed variables entered the equation (Table B). IQR, interquartile ranges. SE, standard error. AUC, area under the curve.

around 110 mg/dL, and postprandial glucose levels <70 mg/dL or >180 mg/dL were very infrequent (Table 4A).

The first component (labelled as *food quantity*) was associated with elevated glucose concentrations from 45 min onwards in the postprandial glucose curve. This effect remained statistically significant throughout the entire monitoring period, increasing glucose concentrations even 6 h after dinner (Fig. 4).

The second component (labelled as *fruit*) was associated with an increased glucose concentration peak 45 min after dinner. However, the effect was short-lived and glucose concentrations decreased early 1 h after dinner. From 2.5 h onwards, the effect of this dimension on glucose concentrations was negative, i.e., it was associated with lower glucose concentrations. This effect was statistically significant up to 6 h after dinner (Fig. 4).

The third component (labelled as *dairy*) showed a double peak effect, at 45 min and 2 h after dinner. The hyperglycemic effect of this component persisted until 6 h after the meal (Fig. 4).

The fourth component (labelled as *starch*) had a prominent effect on postprandial glucose concentrations, as reflected by a higher glucose peak starting 45 min after dinner, reaching a plateau that persisted until 2 h after dinner. The effect of this component gradually decreased from that moment on but remained statistically significant until 4.5 h after dinner (Fig. 4).

Lastly, the fifth component (labelled as *alcohol*) was associated with a negative effect on glucose concentrations, which was statistically significant from 45 min to 3.5 h after dinner (Fig. 4).

In addition to these factors, postprandial glucose levels were influenced by factors related to pre- and post-dinner routines. A longer fasting period before dinner was associated with a higher postprandial glucose concentration peak, with a statistically significant effect lasting until 2.5 h after the dinner. Approximately, for

each additional hour of fasting, a 1 mg/dL increase in the postprandial glucose peak (relative to the intercept curve) was observed (Fig. 4).

The time elapsed between the end of dinner and going to bed was a significant factor in this context, especially when participants delayed their bedtime. The relationship between the time to go to bed and glucose levels was bimodal. The 45-min peak after dinner is likely to be lower, but a rebound effect is observed after 1.5 h. From 1.5 h onwards, glucose levels were higher among the participants still awake compared to those who were already sleeping (Fig. 4).

No statistically significant differences were observed in the postprandial glucose curves between sexes. However, age was associated with a statistically significant effect across all points of the curve. With increasing age, there was an increase in both the baseline glucose level and the postprandial peak, as well as in the rate of glycemic decrease. Specifically, for every 10 years of age, an increase of 2.5 mg/dL was expected at the glucose peak 60 min after dinner (relative to the intercept curve) (Fig. 4).

BMI demonstrated a statistically significant effect on the CGM curve, albeit restricted to the decreasing range of the curve 2 h after dinner onwards. For each kg/m² increase in BMI, there was a corresponding increase of 0.4 mg/dL in glucose levels during the postprandial phase (relative to the reference curve) (Fig. 4).

Table 4B further presents the effect of dinner components, dinner timing, and participant characteristics on mean glucose, analyzing separately the early (0–2 h) and late (2–6 h) postprandial response. These results are in concordance with the results of the multilevel functional regression model (Fig. 4). As the only difference from the previously mentioned results (Fig. 4), this form of analysis revealed a significant effect of sex on the early

postprandial glucose response (0–2 h), with males exhibiting lower glucose levels (Table 4B).

4. Discussion

In this study that analyzed the CGM curves after dinner in adult individuals without diabetes from the general population by means of novel statistical techniques such as PCA and multilevel functional data analysis [33], we observed that the standard glycemic peak curve at 45 min after eating and the subsequent decrease to baseline levels is modified by the participants' characteristics, the nutrient components, and certain pre- and post-dinner routines.

A higher glycemic peak and/or more prolonged hyperglycemia after glucose ingestion are known risk factors for the development of both cardiovascular disease [10] and T2D [5]. It is therefore logical to assume that well-known risk factors for T2D (such as advanced age, elevated BMI, HbA1c at the upper limit of normal, and abnormal fasting glucose levels) are also associated with higher postprandial glucose peaks, as shown by our results.

The type of food ingested also plays a role in postprandial glucose. In real life conditions, nutrient heterogeneity in meals is enormous. PCA helps reduce the dimensionality of the nutrient components without losing much of the information provided by its detailing. Using PCA, we identified 5 dimensions that explain much of the variability of nutrients and corresponded to distinct features of the evening meals that hold specific nutritional interpretations, labelled as food quantity, fruits, dairy products, starch, and alcoholic beverages. Our results confirm that a large intake rich in the starch dimension (i.e., complex carbohydrate-rich foods) is associated with higher postprandial glucose levels [24,25,29], which are maintained several hours after the meal. Carbohydrates are also the main macronutrient in fruits. Our results show that a high consumption of ingredients of the fruit dimension generates a peak of glucose concentration after 45 min. This early glucose peak is noteworthy considering that fructose, the major carbohydrate in fruits (Table 2), has a low glycemic index [48]. The fact that fruits are practically devoid of fats and proteins, nutrients that could attenuate the postprandial hyperglycemic peak [14,22,25,29], might contribute to this early hyperglycemia. However, this peak drops rapidly, to the point that individuals who include fruit in their meal have lower glucose levels from 2.5 h after dinner onwards than individuals who do not include fruit. Theoretically, these data would recommend that individuals without T2D consume fruit to prevent the onset of this disease.

Dairy products are usually a combination of fats (in non-skimmed dairy products) and various saccharides: lactose, galactose, sucrose, and glucose. In our setting, many of the dairy products we consume (yogurts, milkshakes) are also artificially sweetened with sucrose. In this context, we observed that the consumption of dairy ingredients was associated with sustained increased postprandial glucose concentrations. This effect was biphasic, given that the usual glucose concentration peak at 45 min (probably caused by sucrose and glucose) is increased with respect to the reference curve and is followed by a second peak at 2 h. This late-onset peak is possibly due to the fact that lactose is a disaccharide that can raise blood glucose later after being split by lactase into its 2 constituent monosaccharides (glucose and galactose). Another reason for the late rise in glucose levels is the fat that is often a constituent of dairy products [22,25,29].

We also confirmed the well-known postprandial hypoglycemic effect of alcohol. In our study, the hypoglycemic effect of the dimension that is mainly composed of alcoholic beverages is maintained from 30 min to 3.5 h after the meal. According to this effect, previous studies have hypothesized that alcohol might play a protective role in the development of T2D, with inconclusive and

often biased results [49–51]. It should be noted that the mechanism by which alcohol reduces postprandial hyperglycemia is through interference with hepatic gluconeogenesis [16,17], with potential long-term damage to an organ that is essential for glucose metabolism. According to our results, there was almost no hypoglycemia (<70 mg/dL) in the postprandial period, suggesting that, in general, the hypoglycemic effect of alcohol would not be strong enough to cause significant hypoglycemia.

Pre- and post-dinner routines and habits can also affect post-dinner glycemia. Prolonged fasting is associated with higher glucose concentrations between 30 min and 2.5 h after dinner. Previous studies have also shown a “second-meal phenomenon”: compared to skipping lunch, eating lunch is associated with lower blood glucose levels after dinner [30]. It could be hypothesized that prolonged fasting might induce a state of nutrient avidity in the body, leading to more rapid absorption of nutrients after ingestion. Furthermore, it is likely that the participants with longer fasting periods had larger evening meals than those who had shorter fasting periods. Nutritional strategies such as intermittent fasting have the potential to improve glycemic control [52], generating fewer glycemic excursions throughout the day. Based on our results, however, it appears that individuals who fast during the day could have more pronounced hyperglycemia at dinner.

In our study, the participants who went to bed late after dinner had lower glucose levels at 45 min, probably because they were more physically active after dinner than the participants who went to bed early. However, from 90 min onwards, higher glucose levels were observed in the participants who went to bed late than in those who went to bed early. These results are consistent with previous studies that have shown an increased risk of T2D with late bedtimes [53,54], possibly related to hormonal imbalances that occur when the physiological resting pattern is altered.

To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to demonstrate all of these associations in individuals without diabetes using CGM, with glycemic follow-up up to 6 h after dinner. A further strength of the study could be its population design. In contrast to previous studies, our study participants were able to eat freely and then use PCA to simplify the heterogeneity and dimensionality of the nutrients in the foods that made up their evening meals. Thus, there was no need to resort to standardized diets. Standardized diets can be useful tools for evaluating the specific postprandial glucose response pattern of individuals with similar metabolic sets, but they might also be somewhat contrived and removed from real-life situations. In this study, while PCA was effective in capturing general dietary patterns and explaining a substantial portion of the variability in nutrient composition, it is limited in its ability to isolate the individual effects of specific macronutrients on postprandial glucose levels. In a previous study which was focused on the statistical methodology for multilevel functional data analysis [33], we observed that lipids exhibit an initial hypoglycemic effect, followed by an increase in glucose levels. In contrast, fiber demonstrated a later hypoglycemic effect. Proteins, however, exhibited no independent significant impact on postprandial glucose levels. Regarding other study's limitations, its cross-sectional design has inherent temporary ambiguity in the inference of causality, particularly for the future development of T2D, which should be investigated in future studies. As noted above with regard to dairy consumption, many dairy products are artificially sweetened, which is likely to magnify the postprandial hyperglycemia that would occur with an unsweetened dairy product. Our study only investigated the effect of evening meals so as to reduce the potential influence of additional factors such as supplementary food intake, physical activity, and stress that could influence CGM after breakfast or lunch. Future studies are needed to analyze glycemic control throughout the 24-h day considering these

additional factors. Although the accuracy of the CGM system was adequate in most situations, the system was less accurate in the hypoglycemic range, as is the case with most CGM systems [55]. The study was conducted in Spain, where it is customary to eat dinner much later than in most of the rest of the world.

5. Conclusions

The results could have practical implications. First, they reinforce the concept that age [56], obesity, higher fasting glucose levels, and starch consumption [24,25,29] are associated with increased postprandial hyperglycemia. The results also reinforce the recommendation for consuming fruit, given that they demonstrate that this component shows a glycemic-regulating effect for several hours after ingestion, which no study has demonstrated to date. Moreover, our results also make it advisable to go to bed early, given that a late bedtime is associated with higher glucose levels even in individuals who do not eat again after dinner.

Author contributions

TV: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. MCM: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. CFM: Resources, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. JSC: Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing. OLB: Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing. CDL: Formal analysis, Software, Writing – review & editing. MPC: Resources, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. MAS: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. MM: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. FG: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on reasonable request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to Spanish law restrictions.

Funding statement

This study has been funded by Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) through the projects PI11/02219, PI16/01395, PI20/01069; by the European Union (Programme for Research and Innovation, 2021–2027; Horizon Europe, EIC Pathfinder: 101161509-GLUCOTYPES); and by the Network for Research on Chronicity, Primary Care, and Health Promotion, ISCIII, RD21/0016/0022; and co-funded by the European Union-NextGenerationEU. The authors thank Prof. Arturo González-Quintela for criticisms. The A Estrada Glycation and Inflammation Study (AEGIS) group would like to acknowledge the efforts of the participants and thank them for participating.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

References

- Marcelin G, Silveira ALM, Martins LB, Ferreira AV, Clément K. Deciphering the cellular interplays underlying obesity-induced adipose tissue fibrosis. *J Clin Invest* 2019;129:4032–40.
- Ahmed B, Sultana R, Greene MW. Adipose tissue and insulin resistance in obese. *Biomed Pharmacother* 2021;137:111315.
- Nguyen NT, Nguyen XM, Lane J, Wang P. Relationship between obesity and diabetes in a US adult population: findings from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1999–2006. *Obes Surg* 2011;21:351–5.
- Sullivan PW, Morroto EH, Ghushchyan V, Wyatt HR, Hill JO. Obesity, inactivity, and the prevalence of diabetes and diabetes-related cardiovascular comorbidities in the U.S., 2000–2002. *Diabetes Care* 2005;28:1599–603.
- Abdul-Ghani MA, Williams K, DeFronzo R, Stern M. Risk of progression to type 2 diabetes based on relationship between postload plasma glucose and fasting plasma glucose. *Diabetes Care* 2006;29:1613–8.
- Schulze MB, Manson JE, Ludwig DS, Colditz GA, Stampfer MJ, Willett WC, et al. Sugar-sweetened beverages, weight gain, and incidence of type 2 diabetes in young and middle-aged women. *JAMA* 2004;292:927–34.
- Imamura F, O'Connor L, Ye Z, Mursu J, Hayashino Y, Bhupathiraju SN, et al. Consumption of sugar sweetened beverages, artificially sweetened beverages, and fruit juice and incidence of type 2 diabetes: systematic review, meta-analysis, and estimation of population attributable fraction. *BMJ* 2015;351:h3576.
- Fung TT, Schulze M, Manson JE, Willett WC, Hu FB. Dietary patterns, meat intake, and the risk of type 2 diabetes in women. *Arch Intern Med* 2004;164:2235–40.
- Matheus AS, Tannus LR, Cobas RA, Palma CC, Negrato CA, Gomes MB. Impact of diabetes on cardiovascular disease: an update. *Int J Hypertens* 2013;2013:653789.
- Levitan EB, Song Y, Ford ES, Liu S. Is nondiabetic hyperglycemia a risk factor for cardiovascular disease? A meta-analysis of prospective studies. *Arch Intern Med* 2004;25(164):2147–55.
- Lin HJ, Lee BC, Ho YL, Lin YH, Chen CY, Hsu HC, et al. Postprandial glucose improves the risk prediction of cardiovascular death beyond the metabolic syndrome in the nondiabetic population. *Diabetes Care* 2009;32:1721–6.
- Fabricatore AN, Ebbeling CB, Wadden TA, Ludwig DS. Continuous glucose monitoring to assess the ecologic validity of dietary glycemic index and glycemic load. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2011;94:1519–24.
- Henry CJ, Kaur B, Quek RYC. Chrononutrition in the management of diabetes. *Nutr Diabetes* 2020;10:6.
- Smedegaard S, Kampmann U, Ovesen PG, Støvring H, Rittig N. Whey protein premeal lowers postprandial glucose concentrations in adults compared with water-The effect of timing, dose, and metabolic status: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2023;118:391–405.
- Salehi M, Vella A, McLaughlin T, Patti ME. Hypoglycemia after gastric bypass surgery: current concepts and controversies. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 2018;103:2815–26.
- Marks V, Teale JD. Drug-induced hypoglycemia. *Endocrinol Metab Clin N Am* 1999;28:555–77.
- Oba-Yamamoto C, Takeuchi J, Nakamura A, Takikawa R, Ozaki A, Nomoto H, et al. Combination of alcohol and glucose consumption as a risk to induce reactive hypoglycemia. *J Diabetes Invest* 2021;12:651–7.
- Bozzetto L, Pacella D, Cavagnuolo L, Capuano M, Corrado A, Scidà G, et al. Postprandial glucose variability in type 1 diabetes: the individual matters beyond the meal. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2022;192:110089.
- Vetrani C, Calabrese I, Cavagnuolo L, Pacella D, Napolano E, Di Rienzo S, et al. Dietary determinants of postprandial blood glucose control in adults with type 1 diabetes on a hybrid closed-loop system. *Diabetologia* 2022;65:79–87.
- Bell KJ, Smart CE, Steil GM, Brand-Miller JC, King B, Wolpert HA. Impact of fat, protein, and glycemic index on postprandial glucose control in type 1 diabetes: implications for intensive diabetes management in the continuous glucose monitoring era. *Diabetes Care* 2015;38:1008–15.
- Chang CR, Francois ME, Little JP. Restricting carbohydrates at breakfast is sufficient to reduce 24-hour exposure to postprandial hyperglycemia and improve glycemic variability. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2019;109:1302–9.
- Freckmann G, Hagenlocher S, Baumstark A, Jendrike N, Gillen RC, Rössner K, et al. Continuous glucose profiles in healthy subjects under everyday life conditions and after different meals. *J Diabetes Sci Technol* 2007;1:695–703.
- Berry SE, Valdes AM, Drew DA, Asnicar F, Mazidi M, Wolf J, et al. Human postprandial responses to food and potential for precision nutrition. *Nat Med* 2020;26:964–73.
- González-Rodríguez M, Pazos-Couselo M, García-López JM, Rodríguez-Segade S, Rodríguez-García J, Túniz-Bastida C, et al. Postprandial glycemic response in a non-diabetic adult population: the effect of nutrients is different between men and women. *Nutr Metab* 2019;16:46.
- Mendes-Soares H, Raveh-Sadka T, Azulay S, Edens K, Ben-Shlomo Y, Cohen Y, et al. Assessment of a personalized approach to predicting postprandial glycemic responses to food among individuals without diabetes. *JAMA Netw Open* 2019;2:e188102.
- Brynes AE, Adamson J, Dornhorst A, Frost GS. The beneficial effect of a diet with low glycaemic index on 24 h glucose profiles in healthy young people as assessed by continuous glucose monitoring. *Br J Nutr* 2005;93:179–82.
- Black RN, Spence M, McMahon RO, Cuskelly GJ, Ennis CN, McCance DR, et al. Effect of eucaloric high- and low-sucrose diets with identical macronutrient

- profile on insulin resistance and vascular risk: a randomized controlled trial. *Diabetes* 2006;55:3566–72.
- [28] Kim HK, Nanba T, Ozaki M, Chijiki H, Takahashi M, Fukazawa M, et al. Effect of the intake of a snack containing dietary fiber on postprandial glucose levels. *Foods* 2020;9:1500.
- [29] Ando T, Nakae S, Usui C, Yoshimura E, Nishi N, Takimoto H, et al. Effect of diurnal variations in the carbohydrate and fat composition of meals on postprandial glycemic response in healthy adults: a novel insight for the second-meal phenomenon. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2018;108:332–42.
- [30] Kuwahara M, Kim HK, Furutani A, Mineshita Y, Nakaoka T, Shibata S. Effect of lunch with different calorie and nutrient balances on dinner-induced postprandial glucose variability. *Nutr Metab* 2022;19:65. 24.
- [31] Kaur B, Ranawana V, Teh AL, Henry CJK. The impact of a low glycemic index (GI) breakfast and snack on daily blood glucose profiles and food intake in young Chinese adult males. *J Clin Transl Endocrinol* 2015;2:92–8.
- [32] Kaur B, Koh M, Ponnalagu S, Henry CJ. Postprandial blood glucose response: does the glycaemic index (GI) value matter even in the low GI range? *Nutr Diabetes* 2020;10:15.
- [33] Matabuena M, Sartini J, Gude F. Multilevel functional data analysis modelling of human glucose response to meal intake. *ArXiv [Preprint]* 2024. arXiv: 2405.14690v1.
- [34] Gude F, Díaz-Vidal P, Rúa-Pérez C, Alonso-Sampedro M, Fernández-Merino C, Rey-García J, et al. Glycemic variability and its association with demographics and lifestyles in general adult population. *J Diabetes Sci Technol* 2017;11:780–90.
- [35] ElSayed NA, Aleppo G, Aroda VR, Bannuru RR, Brown FM, Bruemmer D, et al. On behalf of the American Diabetes Association. 2. Classification and diagnosis of diabetes: standards of care in diabetes-2023. *Diabetes Care* 2023;46(Suppl 1). S19–S40. Erratum in: *Diabetes Care* 2023;46:1715.
- [36] Craig CL, Marshall AL, Sjöström M, Bauman AE, Booth ML, Ainsworth BE, et al. International physical activity questionnaire: 12-country reliability and validity. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 2003;35:1381–95.
- [37] Gual A, Martos A, Lligona A, Llopis J. Does the concept of a standard drink apply to viticultural societies? *Alcohol Alcohol* 1999;34:153–60.
- [38] Matthews DR, Hosker JP, Rudenski AS, Naylor BA, Treacher DF, Turner RC. Homeostasis model assessment: insulin resistance and beta-cell function from fasting plasma glucose and insulin concentrations in man. *Diabetologia* 1985;28:412–9.
- [39] Ortega R, López-Sobaler A, Andrés P, Requejo A, Aparicio A, Molinero L. DIAL software for assessing diets and food calculations; Department of Nutrition (UCM) & Alceingeniería, SA: Madrid, Spain. 2014. Available online: <http://www.alceingenieria.net/nutricion.htm>. [Accessed 7 December 2023].
- [40] Ortega Anta R, Requejo Marcos A, Nutriguía. Manual de Nutrición Clínica; Editorial Médica Panamericana: Madrid, Spain. 2015. SBN 9788498358674.
- [41] Red BEDCA del Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación. Base de Datos Española de Composición de Alimentos. Available online: <http://www.bedca.net/bdpub/index.php>. [Accessed 7 December 2023].
- [42] U.S. Department of Agriculture ARS. FoodData Central. 2019. Available online: <https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/>. [Accessed 7 December 2023].
- [43] Suh S, Kim JH. Glycemic variability: how do we measure it and why is it important? *Diabetes Metab J* 2015;39:273–82.
- [44] Service FJ. Glucose variability. *Diabetes* 2013;62(5):1398–404.
- [45] DeVries JH. Glucose variability: where it is important and how to measure it. *Diabetes* 2013;62:1405–8.
- [46] Rawlings RA, Shi H, Yuan LH, Brehm W, Pop-Busui R, Nelson PW. Translating glucose variability metrics into the clinic via continuous glucose monitoring: a graphical user interface for diabetes evaluation (CGM-GUIDE®). *Diabetes Technol Therapeut* 2011;13:1241–8.
- [47] Cui E, Li R, Crainiceanu CM, Xiao L. Fast multilevel functional principal component analysis. *J Comput Graph Stat* 2023;32:366–77.
- [48] Jenkins DJ, Wolever TM, Taylor RH, Barker H, Fielden H, Baldwin JM, et al. Glycemic index of foods: a physiological basis for carbohydrate exchange. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1981;34:362–6.
- [49] Knott C, Bell S, Britton A. Alcohol Consumption and the risk of type 2 diabetes: a systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis of more than 1.9 million individuals from 38 observational studies. *Diabetes Care* 2015;38:1804–12.
- [50] Song J, Lin WQ. Association between alcohol consumption and incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus in Japanese men: a secondary analysis of a Retrospective Cohort Study. *BMC Endocr Disord* 2023;23:91.
- [51] Ma H, Wang X, Li X, Heianza Y, Qi L. Moderate alcohol drinking with meals is related to lower incidence of type 2 diabetes. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2022;116:1507–14.
- [52] Che T, Yan C, Tian D, Zhang X, Liu X, Wu Z. Time-restricted feeding improves blood glucose and insulin sensitivity in overweight patients with type 2 diabetes: a randomised controlled trial. *Nutr Metab (Lond)* 2021;18:88.
- [53] Yan B, Fan Y, Zhao B, He X, Yang J, Chen C, et al. Association between late bedtime and diabetes mellitus: a large community-based study. *J Clin Sleep Med* 2019;15:1621–7.
- [54] Ma M, Jiang T, Zhang D, Yao X, Wen Z, Xiu L. Association of bedtime with early-onset diabetes and islet beta cell function in patients with newly diagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nat Sci Sleep* 2023;15:653–62.
- [55] Matheus ASM, Pascoal JBF, Cabizuca CA, Tannus LRM, Guimarães RS, Mattos DMF, et al. Flash glucose monitoring system in patients with type 1 diabetes in healthcare center in Brazil: real world data from a short-term prospective study. *Arch Endocrinol Metab* 2023;67:289–97.
- [56] Basu R, Dalla Man C, Campioni M, Basu A, Klee G, Toffolo G, et al. Effects of age and sex on postprandial glucose metabolism: differences in glucose turnover, insulin secretion, insulin action, and hepatic insulin extraction. *Diabetes* 2006;55:2001–14.